

Derivatives of Aluminium with Glycols and Catechol

R. C. Mehrotra* and R. K. Mehrotra

Reactions of aluminium isopropoxide with glycols (ethylene, 1,3-, 2,3-, 1,4-butylene, hexylene glycols, and pinacol) have been studied. The reaction in the molar ratio of 1:1 affords monoisopropoxy glycolates whereas the reaction with excess of glycols yields diglycolates, except in the case of 2,3-butylene glycol, which gives a tri-derivative. The diglycolates on heating loses a molecule of glycol intermolecularly giving dialuminium triglycolates. The molecular weight determination of soluble aluminium isopropoxy glycolates shows them to have a molecular association of 5-6, whereas dialuminium triglycolate exhibits a tetrameric nature.

The derivatives of aluminium with monohydroxy alcohols have received considerable attention. A fresh light was thrown on the controversy¹⁻³ about their degrees of association by Mehrotra⁴, who observed the "ageing" effect in these compounds. The dimeric nature of aluminium isopropoxide in the vapour phase and aluminium tertiary butoxide in solution exhibited the strength of bridge structure

which is easily explained to be due to the electron-deficient nature of aluminium in monomeric alkoxides and the strong tendency of aluminium to attain a tetra-covalent structure. These have been further confirmed by a study of β -diketone derivatives⁵ of aluminium.

In a recent communication⁶ Bradley has postulated that the metal alkoxides undergo minimum degree of polymerisation consistent with the attainment of maximum covalency of the metal. Aluminium has a strong tendency to show tetra-covalency, but under favourable circumstances it is capable of attaining a hexa-covalent structure. Bradley⁷ has suggested that the "ageing" phenomenon of aluminium alkoxides might be ascribed to the slow tendency of aluminium to increase its co-ordination number from 4 to 6 and has drawn models corresponding to the various degrees (2-6) actually reported by various workers for aluminium alkoxides.

*Present address: Chemistry Dept., University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, Rajasthan.

1. Ulich and Nespital, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1933, **165**, 294.

2. Robinson and Peak, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1935, **39**, 1125.

3. McElvain and Davis, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 1400.

4. Mehrotra, *this Journal*, 1953, **30**, 585.

5. Mehrotra and Mehrotra, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1961, **39**, 795.

6. Bradley, "Metal Alkoxides Review: Progress in Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. II, 1960.

7. Bradley, *Nature*, 1958, **182**, 1211.

Compared to the alkoxides, the derivatives of aluminium with glycols do not seem to have received much attention⁶. A preliminary study of the ethylene glycolate derivatives shows that these are insoluble in organic solvents and this could be ascribed either to chelation or to large-polymer formation. To settle this point, derivatives of a number of glycols were investigated. The reaction of glycols with aluminium isopropoxide in 1:1 molar ratio in presence of benzene can be indicated by the equation:

The reaction was followed by removing and estimating the isopropanol, produced azeotropically with benzene. Derivatives of diethylene and 1,3-, 1,4-, and 2,3-butylene glycols were found to be insoluble in benzene, whereas the corresponding derivatives of pinacol and hexylene glycols were found to be soluble. Ebullioscopic determination of their molecular weights in benzene indicated a molecular association of the order 5-6 (Table I).

The reaction of aluminium isopropoxide with excess of glycols yielded a diglycolate in all the cases excepting 2,3-butanediol which gave a triglycolate derivative. Excess of glycol was removed by washing the products with suitable solvents. These diglycolates on heating lost a molecule of glycol intermolecularly, yielding derivatives with the composition of dialuminium triglycolates in the following way:

All these diglycolates are insoluble in benzene except the hexylene glycolate derivative, where dialuminium trihexylene glycolate exhibits a tetrameric nature in boiling benzene. The pinacol derivative is also slightly soluble in organic solvents.

TABLE I

No.	Compound.	Conc. range per 15 ml of benzene.	Molecular weight.	
			Found.	Calc.
1.	Al(hexyl. glycol) OPr ⁱ	0.0460 — 0.1928 g.	1167	202
2.	Al(pinacol)OPr ⁱ	0.0410 — 0.1077	1088	202
3.	Al ₂ (hexyl. glycol) ₃	0.0650 — 0.1500	1677	402

For the sake of comparison, it was considered of interest to carry out the reactions of aluminium isopropoxide with catechol also, when the following reactions, similar to butan-2,3-diol, were observed.

Some mixed glycollate-catechollates were also prepared by the reactions:

All the catechol derivatives were found insoluble in benzene.

EXPERIMENTAL

All-glass apparatus fitted with interchangeable joints was used throughout and special precautions were taken to exclude moisture. In the alcoholysis experiments, fractionation was carried out in a column packed with Raschig rings and fitted to a total-condensation variable take-off stillhead.

Benzene (B. D. H.) was dried and purified by the method already described⁴. Glycols were distilled carefully before use and catechol (E. Merck) was evacuated at 50°/0.1mm. Dioxane (B. D. H.) and ether were made anhydrous by long storing over sodium wire and finally distilling. Aluminium isopropoxide was prepared as described by Mehrotra⁴.

The molecular weights of compounds were determined by using a modified Gallenkamp semimicro ebulliometer⁹.

Aluminium was determined as oxinate gravimetrically. Isopropanol in the azeotrope was estimated by oxidation with *N*-K₂Cr₂O₇ in 12.5% H₂SO₄ solution⁴. Isopropoxy group in presence of glycols was estimated by liberating the isopropanol from the compound by boiling it in benzene with an excess of glycol and subsequently estimating the isopropanol liberated in benzene-isopropanol azeotrope.

The general synthetic procedure was same in all the cases. Details are recorded for the derivatives of ethylene and hexylene glycols only; the rest of the reactions are summarised in Tables II, III and IV.

⁹ Puri and Mehrotra, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1961, **3**, 247.

TABLE II
Reactions of aluminium isopropoxide with glycols (molar ratio 1:1).

No.	Al(OPri) ₃	Benzene.	Glycol.	Compound formed.	%Aluminium.		Reqd.	% OPri.		Isopropanol liberated in the azeotrope.	
					Found.	Reqd.		Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Calc. (2 moles).
1.	4.90 g.	60 g.	Pinacol (2.87g.)	*Al(pinacol) OPri (4.8 g.)	13.3	13.30	28.5	26.2	2.98 g.	2.88 g.	
2.	4.85	60	Butan-1,3-diol (2.14 g.)	Al(1,3-Bu-diol) OPri (4.0g)	15.7	15.52	33.5	33.9	2.90	2.85	
3.	4.37	60	Butan-2,3-diol (1.9g.)	Al(2,3-Bu-diol) OPri (3.7g)	15.5	15.52	33.4	33.9	2.50	2.57	
4.	4.20	60	Butan-1,4-diol (1.88g.)	Al(1,4-Bu-diol) OPri (3.5g)	15.5	15.52	33.6	33.9	2.50	2.47	

TABLE III
Reactions of aluminium isopropoxide with glycols (molar ratio 1: >3).

No.	Al(OPri) ₃	Benzene.	Glycol.	Compound formed.	%Aluminium.		Reqd.	Isopropanol liberated in the azeotrope.	
					Found.	Reqd.		Found.	Calc. (3 moles)
1.	3.32 g.	60 g.	Pinacol (10.6g.)	Al(pinacol) ₃	10.4	10.38	10.38	2.73 g.	2.90 g.
2.	3.70	50	Butan-1,3-diol (9.4g.)	*Al(1,3-Bu-diol) ₂	13.4	13.24	13.24	3.15	3.30
3.	2.90	60	Butan-2,3-diol (8.6g.)	Al(2,3-Bu-diol) ₃	8.8	9.18	9.18	2.54	2.55
4.	2.76	50	Butan-1,4-diol (8.1g.)	Al(1,4-Bu-diol) ₃	13.4	13.24	13.24	2.30	2.40

*Bu-diol denotes butan-diol.

TABLE IV
Reactions of aluminium isopropoxide with catechol (in molar ratios 1:1, 1:2, and 1:3).

No.	Al(OPri) ₃	Benzene.	Catechol.	Compound formed.	%Aluminium.		Reqd.	% OPri.		Isopropanol liberated in the azeotrope.	
					Found.	Reqd.		Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Calc.
1.	3.48 g. (1 mole)	60 g.	1.87 g. (1 mole)	Al(C ₆ H ₄ O ₂) OPri	14.1	13.90	20.4	30.4	2.00 g.	2.04g. (2 moles)	
2.	3.37 (1 mole)	70	3.6 g. (2 moles)	Al(C ₆ H ₄ O ₂) (C ₆ H ₅ O ₂)	11.3	11.06	..	..	2.70 (3 moles)	2.9 g.	
3.	1.88 (1 mole)	60	3.04 g. (3 moles)	Al(C ₆ H ₅ O ₂) ₃	7.8	7.62	..	..	1.64 (3 moles)	1.66 g.	

Reactions between Aluminium Isopropoxide and Ethylene Glycol

(i) *In 1:1 Molar Ratio.*—Aluminium isopropoxide (2.9 g.), glycol (0.88 g.), and benzene (60 ml) were shaken to give a white suspension. This was refluxed followed by slow fractionation of isopropanol. A white solid separated which after removing benzene was dried under reduced pressure at 60° to furnish a white powder (2.0 g.). Found: 1.56 g. isopropanol in the azeotrope against 1.7 g. (calc. for 2 moles in aluminium isopropoxide taken). [Found: Al, 18.0; OPrⁱ, 41.6. Al(C₂H₄O₂)OPrⁱ requires Al, 18.4; OPrⁱ, 40.4%].

The same experiment was repeated in refluxing ether and the product isolated. (Found: Al, 18.0; OPrⁱ, 40.7%).

(ii) *In 2:3 Molar Ratio.*—Aluminium isopropoxide (3.69 g.) was admitted to glycol (1.41 g.) in benzene (70 ml). On shaking a white, finely divided suspension was obtained. This was refluxed under a column and the isopropanol-benzene azeotrope fractionated. A colorless mass separated. After decanting the benzene, the solid was dried under reduced pressure. Found: 2.7 g. isopropanol in the azeotrope against 2.72 g. (calc. for 3 moles in aluminium isopropoxide taken). [Found: Al, 22.2; glycol, 75.3. Al₂(C₂H₄O₂)₃ requires Al, 23.0; glycol, 76.92%].

The above reaction was carried out in refluxing ether also to give a white solid. (Found: Al, 22.2; glycol, 75.8%).

(iii) *With Excess of Ethylene Glycol.*—Aluminium isopropoxide (5.3 g.), glycol (9.6 g.), and benzene (60 ml) on shaking gave a white precipitate. Isopropanol liberated was fractionated, leaving a residue along with benzene, which was filtered in a dry atmosphere, washed with dioxane, and dried at 40°/0.1 mm to afford a white powder (3.4 g.), insoluble in benzene and dioxane. (Found: Al, 18.0; glycol, 81.1. Al(C₂H₄O₂)(C₂H₅O₂) requires Al, 18.2; glycol, 81.75%).

Reaction of Aluminium Mono-isopropoxyglycollate with Catechol (1:1).—Catechol (0.56 g.) was added to a suspension of Al(C₂H₄O₂)OPrⁱ (0.74 g.) in benzene (40 ml) to give a white suspension. Isopropanol produced in the reaction was fractionated leaving a residue with benzene, which was dried at 60°/0.1 mm to give a powder (0.9 g.). Found: 0.29 g. isopropanol in the azeotrope against 0.30 g. (calc. for 1 mole). [Found: Al, 13.2. Al(C₂H₄O₂)(C₆H₃O₂) requires Al, 13.7%].

Reaction between Aluminium Mono-isopropoxy catechollate with Glycol (1:1).—A mixture of glycol (0.42 g.) and Al(C₂H₄O₂)OPrⁱ (1.32 g.) in benzene (60 ml) gave a suspension. On refluxing and fractionating the alcohol as usual, a greyish powder, insoluble in benzene, was obtained. Found: 0.39 g. isopropanol in the azeotrope against 0.4g. (calc. for 1 mole). [Found: Al, 13.4. Al(C₂H₄O₂)(C₂H₅O₂) requires Al, 13.7%].

Reactions between Aluminium Isopropoxide and Hexylene Glycol

(a) *In 1:1 Ratio.*—Aluminium isopropoxide (3.0 g.) was admitted to a solution of hexylene glycol (1.74 g.) in benzene (40 ml) to give a clear solution. After refluxing under a column, isopropanol produced in the reaction was fractionated dropwise till the temperature of the distillate was steady at 80° and showed no tendency to decrease. After distilling excess of benzene, a small amount of a liquid was left in the reaction flask which was

evaporated under reduced pressure to furnish a white crystalline solid (2.95 g.), readily soluble in benzene. Found: 1.70 g. isopropanol in the azeotrope against 1.76 g. (calc. for 2 moles of aluminium isopropoxide taken). [Found Al, 13.3%; OPrⁱ, 28.4. (C₆H₁₂O₂)₃AlOPrⁱ requires Al, 13.3; OPrⁱ, 29.2%].

On distillation of the above compound, a residue, insoluble in benzene, was obtained at bath temperature of 300°/0.1 mm.

(b) *In 2:3 Ratio*.—A mixture of aluminium isopropoxide (2.57 g.), hexylene glycol (2.23 g.), and benzene (50 ml) gave a clear solution which was refluxed followed by dropwise fractionation of isopropanol-benzene azeotrope coming at 72°. After removing excess of benzene at a high reflux ratio (1:20), the residue in the reaction flask was dried to provide a white crystalline solid (2.53 g.), soluble in benzene. Amount of isopropanol in the azeo trope was found 2.17 g. against 2.26 g. (calculated for 3 moles). Found: Al, 13.1. Al₂(C₆H₁₂O₂)₃ requires Al, 13.4%].

(c) *In 1: > 3 Ratio*.—A mixture of aluminium isopropoxide (3.0 g.), hexylene glycol (6.5 g.), and benzene (50 ml) was refluxed under a column to give a clear solution. This was followed by dropwise fractionation of isopropanol-benzene azeotrope till temperature of the distillate was constant at 80°. In the end, after distilling excess of benzene a little liquid was left. Excess of hexylene glycol was distilled at 110°/0.91 mm, leaving a crystalline solid, soluble in benzene. Total amount of isopropanol in the azeotrope was found to be 2.55 g. against 2.64 g. (calculated for 3 moles). [Found: Al, 13.1. Al₂(C₆H₁₂O₂)₃ requires Al, 13.4%].

Thanks of the authors are due to the Council of Scientific & Industrial Research, New Delhi, for providing a fellowship to one of them (R. K. M.).